

Mechanisms of Economic Analysis of Marketing Activities

AUTHOR(S): DR. GULSARAKHON M. OSTONAKULOVA,
JALILOV JAMSHID GANIJONOVICH,
AND
MUXSINOV BEKZOD TOXIROVICH,

Abstract

The article proposes an algorithm for a complex economic analysis of marketing activities with a description of the tasks and methods of analysis at each stage of the sequence of mechanisms. The sources, process and results of marketing activities are analyzed in order to identify trends, behaviors, resources and opportunities to increase the effectiveness of marketing activities.

Keywords: mechanisms of economic analysis of marketing activities, comprehensive analysis of marketing activities, marketing indicators, financial indicators,

IJOBAS

Accepted 25 May 2021
Published 31 May 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4994496

About Author

Author(s):

DR. GULSARAKHON M. OSTONAKULOVA,
Associate Professor in Marketing department of
Tashkent State University of Economics, Uzbekistan.

JALILOV JAMSHID GANIJONOVICH,
PhD in Marketing department of Tashkent state university of
economics, Uzbekistan.

AND

MUXSINOV BEKZOD TOXIROVICH,
Bukhara state university, teacher of the department
"Economics of the service sector", Uzbekistan.

Introduction.

Economic analysis of marketing activities has important specific features that distinguish it from the analysis of economic or other activities of the enterprise. We can distinguish the whole range of such features: the specificity of resource analysis, the process of marketing activities, the specificity of the analysis of the share of marketing activities in the results of the enterprise, the relevance of the results of the analysis of marketing activities; mechanisms)[1]. Analysis of both marketing activities and in terms of specific areas: functions, projects, programs, brands, distribution channels, customer (customer flow) units. [2]

Economic analysis of marketing activities can lead to inaccurate indicators and conclusions about the use of marketing activities resources, the effectiveness and efficiency of marketing activities, without taking into account its specific features in the generally accepted methods[3]. Developing a sequence and applying the techniques of economic analysis of marketing activities to interested users (head of marketing and economic services, enterprise director) to make effective marketing decisions, rational use of resources of marketing activities, find ways to improve marketing results, identify resources and opportunities, as well as allows you to identify shortcomings in the organization of marketing activities.

Research methodology.

It is necessary to apply a comprehensive approach in the economic analysis of marketing activities, because as a single systemic process, there is a target orientation of enterprises to the integrated management of marketing activities[4]. The complexity of the economic analysis of marketing activities is the study of all areas of marketing activities (in terms of functions, units, brands, markets, marketing programs, etc.), the use of different types and methods of economic analysis of marketing activities, describing the economic, strategic and social components means the need to use indicators[5].

Analysis and expected results.

The economic analysis of marketing activities includes the initial and four main stages: Management of general indicators of marketing activities, a detailed description of the indicators related to the field under study, the formation of conclusions and recommendations. Let's take a closer look at the functions of each stage of the economic analysis mechanism of marketing activities.

1. The initial stage.

1.1. Defining the goals and objectives of the research.

1.1.1. Determining the type of analysis depending on the completeness of the questions studied: complex, thematic, local[6].

1.1.2. Improving the research object in the context of thematic (analysis of resources (costs), process or results, functions, brands or sales segments, etc.) or local analysis (analysis of advertising activities, analysis of marketing solution effectiveness or loss-making market segment).

1.1.3. Determining the goals and objectives of the analysis depending on the type of analysis and the object of study (study of causal relationships, identification of reserves, determination of the contribution of marketing activities).

1.2. Collection of the obtained data, initial processing[7].

1.2.1. Gathering the necessary information: an economic report prepared as part of the study, management accounting and analysis of the initial and final documents of the financial statements.

1.2.2. Check the accuracy and truthfulness of the information.

1.2.3. Preparation of information materials for reading (for example, using the method of presenting tables).

1.3. Calculation of indicators of the object of study.

1.3.1. Select and justify a set of indicators (indicators that describe the economic, strategic or social aspects of marketing activities) that meet the stated goals and objectives.

1.3.2. Calculate the required indicators for the required period[8].

2. Office of general indicators of marketing activities (typical for marketing activities in general).

2.2. The structure of economic analysis, the dynamics of indicators of marketing activities.

2.2.1. Financial analysis includes the availability, movement, composition and dynamics of resources (primarily financial and labor), variable and conditional fixed costs, identification of negative growth trends of poorly managed and unplanned costs: identification of economic functions, identification of primary and secondary dynamics, identification of unnecessary costs.

2.2.2. Analysis of the structure and dynamics of indicators of marketing operations, ie. determine whether a marketing activity performed using qualitative measurement meets the requirements for input data structure (e.g., appropriateness, completeness, and reliability of the data collected), and dynamically review these indicators in the context of units, functions, programs, and projects.

2.2.3. Analysis of the structure and dynamics of economic indicators (financial: profit, profitability; non-financial (market): market share, penetration rate); dynamics of changes in indicators that characterize strategic (changes in customer behavior (changes in the number of new, retained customers)) and relationships (changes in popularity, satisfaction); and social (changes in employee satisfaction) results [9].

2.3. Comparing resources (costs), sub-processes (operations), actual and key performance indicators of marketing activities, identification of deviations from the established criteria, plans, limits approved in accordance with strategic and operational marketing objectives, product life cycle, external market conditions.

2.4. Ability to identify factors and causes of deviations in the results of costs and marketing activities, to calculate the impact of factors by deterministic and stochastic factors analysis, to group the factors according to positive or negative effects, to regulate.

2.5. Solving the problems of economic analysis specific to marketing activities: the need to measure marketing results in the form of indicators that contribute to the results of the enterprise, the features of calculating the cost-effectiveness of marketing activities associated with the result itself and its cost, the need to study such economic consequences (profits, financial losses) . strategic and social outcomes such as satisfaction, customer loyalty, reputation, image.

2.6. Identification of resources, opportunities to increase the efficiency, effectiveness and effectiveness of marketing activities.

3. Full indicators can be carried out in all areas of marketing activities and economic analysis, as well as in the framework of thematic or local analysis in certain areas or objects. Depending on the scale, importance, costs, level of development of marketing in the enterprise, as well as the conditions of analysis (relevance, availability of the subject of analysis), the study can be divided into parts. During the transition to analysis, sections, projects, decisions, functions, and other tasks in the analysis blocks can be configured [10].

4. The conclusions of the analysis are formed in accordance with the initial tasks: the structure of marketing activities, conclusions about dynamic processes, characteristics of marketing activities, conclusions about behavior, implementation of dynamic criteria, cause and effect relationships of marketing elements, influencing factors, conclusions conclusions. Contributions of marketing activities, accurate measurement of the results of marketing activities, conclusions about stocks and unused opportunities in the specific conditions of the internal and external environment[11].

5. The final stage of the analysis is to correct the mechanism of transition of marketing activities to economic analysis and formulate recommendations for new marketing decisions.

Conclusions and suggestions.

The mechanism of transition of marketing activities to economic analysis is cyclical and ongoing. The mechanism of transition of marketing activities to economic analysis prevents the adoption and completion of management decisions before marketing planning, as well as participates in the process of organizing and regulating the effectiveness of marketing decisions.

The mechanism of transition of the provided marketing activity to economic analysis covers all tasks of the marketing activity analysis and can be performed annually or for several years. To speed up the analytical process, to conduct research on point problems, marketing activity analyzes may have a truncated or simplified form, but at the same time, the logic of block building and analysis sequence is retained in the diagram, making it official for making various marketing decisions. allows you to use it as a basis.

References:

- Abdukarimov, I.T. Problems of economic analysis in modern conditions of economic development / I.T. Abdukarimov, I.F. Narijnyy // Sotsialno-ekonomicheskie yavleniya i protsessy. - 2010.
- Budrin, A.G. Marketing obespechenie predpriyatiya / A.G. Budrin, V.N. Tatarenko // Problems of modern economics. - 2012.
- Djasurovna, S. (2020). Marketing asoslari. Архив научных исследований, 1(12).
извлечено от <https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/1492>
- Djasurovna, S. (2020). Strategik marketing Toshkent –. Архив научных исследований, 1(13). извлечено от
<https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/1547>
- Djasurovna, S. (2020). Тармоқлар ва соҳалар маркетинги. Архив научных исследований, 1(21). извлечено от
<https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/1396>
- Ganijonovich, J. J. (2016). Importance motivational methods on marketing management in the light industry enterprises. SAARJ Journal on Banking & Insurance Research, 5(2), 1-13.
- Gabdullina, G.K. Development of methods of economic analysis in the work of modern economists / G.K. Gabdullina // Vestnik ekonomiki, prava i sotsiologii. - 2013.
- Jalilov, J. (2020). Корхоналарнинг маркетинг фаолиятида мотивация усулларини қўллаш зарурати. Архив научных исследований, 33(1).
- Jalilov, J. (2020). Маркетингда истеъмолчига йўналтирилган мотивация назариялари. Архив научных исследований, 33(1).
- Jalilov, J. G. (2017). Hedonic motivations among uzbek consumers. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 7(51), 34- 41.

Jalilov, J. G. (2018). Use of Motivation Methods used to Motivate Media in Light Industry Enterprises. Economics and Innovative Technologies, 2018(5), 25.

Cite this article:

Author(s), DR. GULSARAKHON M. OSTONAKULOVA, JALILOV JAMSHID GANIJONOVICH, MUXSINOV BEKZOD TOXIROVICH, (2021). "Mechanisms of Economic Analysis of Marketing Activities". **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 153- 158. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4994496>, Issue: 5, Vol.: 3, Article: 19, Month: May, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

